

Computation of Summations of Annamalai's Binomial Expansions

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Abstract: This paper presents a technique to compute the sum of Annamalai's binomial expansions. This computing technique is a sort of methodological advance which is used for researchers working in computational science, computation, cryptography, combinatorics, discrete mathematics, and theoretical computer science.

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1. Introduction

Computational science is a rapidly growing multi-and inter-disciplinary area where science, engineering, mathematics, statistics, computation, and collaboration use advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real life problems. In this article, we provide a theorem based on the Annamalai's binomial coefficient and identity. The results of Annamalai's binomial coefficients and identities [1- 6] are useful to solve the scientific problems in computational science.

For basic understanding, the traditional coefficient and optimized coefficient are given below:

Traditional coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N \cup \{0\}$ & $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized coefficient: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \text{ \& } V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Computation of Binomial Expansions

Theorem: $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} - 1$.

Proof: The theorem is proved using the Annamalai's binomial identity [1 - 6].

Annamalai's binomial identity is $V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n \dots + V_{r-1}^n + V_r^n = V_r^{n+1}$

$$\Rightarrow V_0^{n-1} + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-1} + V_3^{n-1} \dots + V_r^{n-1} = V_r^n.$$

From this binomial identity, we can prove the theorem step by step.

Step 1: $V_0^0 + V_1^0 + V_2^0 + V_3^0 + \dots + V_r^0 = V_r^1$.

Step 2: $V_0^1 + V_1^1 + V_2^1 + V_3^1 + \dots + V_r^1 = V_r^2$.

Step 3: $V_0^2 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 + V_3^2 + \dots + V_r^2 = V_r^3$.

Step 4: $V_0^3 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 + \dots + V_r^3 = V_r^4$.

Similarly, we can continue the binomial expansions up to “step n ”.

$$\text{Step } n: V_0^{n-1} + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-1} + V_3^{n-1} + \dots + V_r^{n-1} = V_r^n.$$

By adding these binomial expansions on both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n.$$

$$\text{Note that } \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n \dots + V_r^n = V_r^{n+1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} - V_0^n, (V_0^n = 1).$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} - 1.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem based on the summation of the Annamalai’s binomial expansions has been proved by using the Annamalai’s binomial coefficients and application [7]. This is a sort of methodological advance which is used for researchers working in computational science, computation, cryptography, combinatorics, discrete mathematics, and theoretical computer science.

References

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